

ISic0433

Funerary stone of Gn. Julius Felix

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Roma

Place of origin (modern)

Rome

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 237

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

- 1.
2. D(is) M(anibus)
3. Cn(aeus) · Iulius Fe
4. lix · Cn(aeo) · Iulio
5. Felici filio
6. qui vix(it) · ann(os)
7. II · men(sis) · VIII
8. die(s) · uno
9. [---]

Apparatus

Text of CIL

Translation (en)

To the shades of the underworld. Gnaeus Julius Felix (made this) for his son Gnaeus Julius Felix who lived two years, nine months and one day

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491661

EDCS 21900495

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.7153 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/item/buchseite/6507683>)

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Henzen, W., Zangemeister, K. F. W. 1872-1913. Ephemeris epigraphica. Corporis inscriptionum Latinarum supplementum, edita iussu Instituti archaeologici Romani. Berlin. At VIII 681

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-17): ISic0433. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4335656>